

Justice in Aid : A Socio Legal Study of Victim Compensation with special reference to Manodhairya Scheme

- Jadhavar P. S.*

*Asst. Prof., Department of Law, Shivaji University, Kolhapur

Victim compensation has emerged as a pivotal aspect of restorative justice, aiming to provide monetary relief and psychological rehabilitation to individuals who have suffered harm due to criminal acts. In India while the criminal justice system predominantly focuses on punishing offenders the victims need for immediate financial support and emotional healing often remain secondary. The Manodhairya Scheme introduced by government of Maharashtra in 2013. Represents significant policy initiative to address this gap by offering financial assistance, counselling and rehabilitation measures to survivors of rape, acid attacks and certain other forms of violence. This socio-legal study critically examines the framework, objectives and implementation of victim compensation with special reference to Kolhapur. This research paper explores the schemes legal underpinnings within the wider context in state level victim compensation model in India.

Key words : BNS, BNA, BNSS

Introduction

Justice is not only about punishing criminal; it is also about helping and supporting the people who suffer because of crime. Victims often go through physical pain, mental stress, emotional trauma, and financial loss. For a long time, the criminal justice system in India mostly focused on catching and punishing the accused while the needs of victims especially women and children were ignored. After certain timespan, society and law started realizing that justice should also mean helping victim's recovery.

This is how the idea of victim compensation developed. Victim compensation is a system of serious crimes such as rape, sexual assault, acid attack or human trafficking are given financial help, counselling and support for rehabilitation. The idea comes from the principle that the state has a duty not only to protect its people but also to care for them when they are harmed. These shows a shift from the old system of justice, which focused only on punishment (retributive justice) to a new system that focuses on healing and repairing the damage done (restorative justice).

Importance of victim compensation Scheme:

The traditional criminal justice system in India has been offender- focused and concentrating on punishing the wrongdoer while overlooking the needs of victims. The victim compensation scheme is significant because it highlights the shift towards a victim-centric approach, emphasizing that justice is incomplete without addressing the trauma, rehabilitation and dignity of victims. By analyzing both legal framework (such as Article

21 and sec 397 of BNSS) and the functioning of state schemes like Manodhairya, which bridges the gap between law and society.

Objectives:

1. To understand the concept and study the evolution of victim compensation scheme.
2. To examine the socio- legal framework of victim compensation scheme.
3. To study the structure and functioning of Manodhairya scheme.
4. To evaluate the effectiveness of Manodhairya scheme and practice.

Hypothesis

Hypothesis is tentative statement, assumption or proposition that researcher make in order to explain the fact.

1. Special protection is justified for women and children.
2. Compensation should not be depend on conviction.

Manodhairya scheme significance in victim compensation

“This scheme also called as rehabilitation scheme launched by government of Maharashtra in October 2013. The word Manodhairya means courage or mental strength. In addition, the scheme aims to provide financial aid, emotional support and rehabilitation to victims of heinous crimes such as rape, child sexual abuse and acid attacks. This scheme provide immediate financial assistance and long-term rehabilitation of victims of sexual offences and acid attacks. It will help victims to recover mentally, physically and socially. The scheme especially targets the most vulnerable groups who not just suffer from crime but also from social rejection, stigma and lifelong trauma. Under this scheme, victims given financial help depending upon the nature and seriousness of the crime. In cases of rape and child sexual abuse, victims can receive compensation ranging from 2 lakhs to 10 lakh depending on severity of the crime and the situation of the victim. Victims of acid attack are entitled to compensation of up to 10 lakh, which is decided based on the extent of burns, disfigurement or disability caused by attack”.

“In cases where victim dies, the compensation provided to the family or dependents of the victims. The financial support meant to cover important needs such as medical treatment, education, daily living expenses and long term rehabilitation so that the victim or their family can cope with the losses and rebuild their lives”.

Indian Constitution and Manodhairya scheme

“Manodhairya scheme based on Indian Constitution Article 14 Equality before law. Equal protection means the state has to ensure not only punishment for offenders but also relief for victims. Indian constitution article 15(3) permits the state to make special provision for women and children. Manodhairya scheme is victim centric, fits under this protective principle. Under the Article 21 everyone has right to life and dignity. Supreme Court has held that the right to life includes rehabilitation and compensation for victims of crime. The scheme directly implements this interpretation by ensuring monetary and

non-monetary support. Indian Constitution Directive principle of state policy Article 39 explain the concept access to justice. Justice is not meaningful unless victims can rebuild their lives by funding medical care, education and legal assistance”.

Statutory framework

“NALSA (National Legal Services Authority) guidelines issued to all states for uniform victim compensation schemes and Manodhairya aliens with it. In International obligations, India is signatory to CEDAW (Convention on Elimination of All form of Discrimination against Women) and CRC (Convention on Rights of Child). These conventions bounds to protect and rehabilitate victims of gender based violence. Manodhairya serves as a domestic fulfillment of these commitments”.

“In the year, 2009 CRPC amended to insert Section 357A which obligates every state to prepare a victim Compensation scheme. This Section explains that State government in coordination with state legal services Authorities must provide compensation to victims of crime. Manodhairya is Maharashtra’s legal compliance with Sec 357A. It gives the provision a practical form, authorities and procedures”.

Definition of Victim under Manodhairya scheme.

“According to the Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sahita 2024 Sec 2(Y) defines that a person who has suffered loss or injury caused by reason of the act or omission of the accused person includes the legal hair or guardian of such victim”.

International framework for victim compansation

“UN General Assembly Declaration of “Basic principles of Justice for Victims and Abuse of Power” adopted in 1985. In these basic principles of Justice for victims and abuse of power highlights the rights of victims. The rights of victims included following rights”.

- Restitution
- Compensation
- Assistance
- Access to justice and fair treatment

“The meaning of restitution elaborates that the compensation made by criminal himself ordered by criminal court. The UN General Assembly passed a resolution tiled “Basic Principles and Guidelines on the Right to remedy and Repartitions for Victims of Gross Violations of International Human Rights Law and serious Violations of International humanitarian Law 2005.”

Judicial Interpretation

“In various cases Hon’ble Supreme Court and Hon’ble High Court has emphasized state liability to compensats victims in Bodhisatva Gautam vs Subhra Chakraborty (1996) and Delhi Domestic working Women’s Forum vs Union of India. Maharashtra’s scheme reflects these judicial directions by providing immediate relief without waiting for outcome of criminal trials. Court often directs state authorities to consider Manodhairya claims in pending cases reinforcing its legal standard”.

Analysis

Above chart represents three-year data collection from Kolhapur for analysis. In the year 2018, eighty-three cases registered under this scheme. Eighty-one cases successfully awarded compensation within that one year. In the 2019 year, thirty-five cases registered under this scheme. Nineteen cases were awarded compensation within that year. In the 2020 year, twenty-two cases registered. Only seven cases awarded compensation that year. In the year 2021, fifty-eight cases registered among them only eight cases awarded for compensation. In the year 2022, two hundred and fifteen cases were registered among them one hundred and fifty two cases were awarded for compensation. In the year, 2023 until the month of April fifty-two cases were registered and among them thirty-five cases awarded compensation. According to this, data DLSA play significant role in victim compensation scheme.

Conclusion

“Manodhairya scheme represents reformative approach by Maharashtra government to address the needs of victims. By providing substantial financial aid and comprehensive rehabilitation services, the scheme aims to empower victims to rebuild their lives with dignity and confidence. However, continuous monitoring and evaluation are essential to ensure its effective implementation and to address any challenges that may arise in reaching all eligible beneficiaries. Its integrated model of immediate relief, structured compensation and comprehensive rehabilitation sets example in society. Above chart represents three-year data collection from Kolhapur for analysis Its true success relies on consist ant and timely delivery of benefits, sensitivity in handling trauma-induced inconsistencies and reforms to eliminate provisions that may inadvertently penalize survivors for actions stemming from distress. This scheme maintain balance with strong safeguards against misuse the scheme has the potential to not just compensate victims but to genuinely help them rebuild their lives with dignity and resilience”.

Findings

1. “Manodhairya scheme has provided crucial financial and psychological support to victims.
2. State government effectively execute their responsibility.
3. Bureaucratic delays, lack of fund, and poor follow-up crate hurdle in implementation of scheme.
4. Requirement of various documents pose hurdles for marginalized victims in accessing compensation”.

Suggestions

1. “Simplify procedures ensures time bound disbursal of time bound disbursal of compensation and strengthen awareness and victim support mechanism for better implementation.
2. Need to provide interim relief after the registration of FIR.
3. Need time bound service under Manodhairya scheme.

4. Mandatory to establish mechanism to track the cases”.

References

1. V.S.R. Avadhani,V & Soubhagya Valli. “Sentencing and Victim Compensation-Principles and Practices” Asia Law house (2014).
2. Ginsburg William L. “Victims’ Rights: A Complete Guide to Crime Victim Compensation” Galt Pr (1993)
3. Sanjeev P. Sahni” Victims Assistance in India Suggestive Legislative Reform: A Comprehensive Comparative Policy Review” Ane Books (2019)
4. Sahni, Sanjeev P., Palit, Manjushree and Dhanda, Astha (2017) Victims’ assistance in India- suggesting legislative reform: a comprehensive comparative policy review. Ane Books, New Delhi.
5. Sky Thakur “ Victim Compensation in India Criminal Justice System” LAP Lambert Academic Publishing (2013)
6. <https://www.viplafoundation.org/Manodhariya-Scheme-Handbook.pdf>.